

ESTIMATION OF ZINC IN SNAKE VENOMS BY MICRO-QUINALDINATE METHOD.

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Percentage of zinc in various types of Indian snake venoms has been determined microchemically by means of sodium quinaldinate. It has been found that the zinc content varies from 0.56% in the case of *naja naja* cobra venom to less than 0.02% for *Bungarus ceruleus* among the colubrides, and from 0.186% in the case of *Echis carinata* to 0.04% for *Russell's viper* among the viperides. In purified neurotoxin and haemolysin fractions of *Naja naja* cobra venom the zinc percentage is reduced to negligible amount. The results indicate that there is no relationship between the zinc content of the crude venom and its toxicity as was previously assumed by Delezenne. The sensitivity and the reliability of the quinaldinate method for the estimation of minute quantities of zinc in biological materials are thus clearly demonstrated.

Zinc has been found to be a constant constituent of all animal cells. Delezenne (*Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1919, 33, 68) found that in the venom of serpents it is present to the extent of 0.31-0.56% in colubrides and 0.11-0.23% in viperides. According to his observations the proportion of zinc in the venom was found to vary inversely with the coagulating and proteolytic properties of the latter and directly with its nucleolytic and haemolytic activities.

The method of estimation adopted by Delezenne was the usual macro-method of precipitation as sulphide and ignition of the latter into oxide. As the estimation of small quantities of zinc by this macro-method is not likely to give very accurate results for the purpose of such comparisons between toxicity and zinc content of venoms, it was considered desirable to determine the zinc content of the venoms of certain Indian snakes by using a more dependable and refined method. Sodium quinaldinate was, therefore, selected as the most suitable reagent for the micro-chemical estimation of zinc in the venoms (Rây and Bose, *Mikrochemie*, 1935, 17, 11).

It was also of interest to re-examine this problem, since Slotta and Fraenkel-Conrat (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1078) in their work on the rattle snake (*Crotalus t. terrificus*) venom failed to detect the presence of zinc either in the crude venom or in the crystalline poison Crotoxin, isolated by them from the venom.

Seven different types of Indian snake venoms were analysed for zinc in our laboratory. Five of these are colubrides, such as cobra venoms—*Naja naja*, *Naja tripudians*, *Naja bungarus*, and the krait venoms—*Bungarus fasciatus* and *Bungarus ceruleus*. The other two are viperides—viz.,

Vipera russellii and *Echis carinata*. Zinc was found and estimated in all these crude venoms. The smallest percentage was found in *Bungarus ceruleus*. Though the maximum amount (0.56%) found in colubride venoms (i.e. *Naja naja*) corresponds closely with that obtained by Delezenne, there is, however, considerable discrepancy in the case of lower limit for both the colubrides and viperides ($\approx 0.02\%$ in *Bungarus ceruleus* and 0.04% in Russell's viper). Further, contrary to Delezenne's observations the toxicity in the two viperide venoms examined does not run parallel with the zinc content. The same holds good also with the colubride venoms.

The following table gives a comparative idea about the zinc content and the different aspects of activity of the venom.

TABLE I.

Venoms	Neurotoxic activity (same as the toxicity value).	Haemolytic activity.	Coagulating power.	Proteolytic power.	Zinc content (average).
<i>Naja Bungarus</i>	0.0033 mg.	Not determined.	...	+	0.04%
<i>Naja naja</i>	0.035	+++	...	+	0.554
<i>Naja tripudians</i>	0.030	+++	...	+	0.457
<i>B. ceruleus</i>	0.0009	+++	...	+	0.02
<i>B. fasciatus</i>	0.370	++	...	+	0.0253
<i>Echis carinata</i>	0.0093	+	+	++	0.186
<i>Vipera russellii</i>	0.020	Less than <i>Echis</i>	++	+	0.04

(+ indicates moderate, ++ indicates high, +++ very high, ... indicates nil.)

The purified neurotoxin and haemolysin factors of *Naja naja* cobra venoms (Ghosh and De, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, 25, 779) were then examined for zinc content. The neurotoxin factors gave a rather low value (0.15 and 0.04% Zn), whereas haemolysin factor was practically free from it. It is quite likely that with further purification the neurotoxin factor will also be found to be free from zinc. Obviously, zinc cannot be regarded as an essential constituent of the poison, present in the crude venom.

Method of Estimation.

Among the inorganic constituents of snake venom calcium, magnesium, sulphur and phosphorus were detected besides zinc. None of these elements interfere with the estimation of zinc as quinaldinate.

About 0.08-0.15 g. of the venom was treated with 1 c.c. of fuming nitric acid and 1 c.c. of perchloric acid in a small 50 c.c. beaker covered with a watch-glass. This was at first heated on the water-bath and then over an asbestos board. Thick white fumes of perchloric acid came out and the mixture was evaporated to dryness. The residue was again treated with a small quantity of perchloric and fuming nitric acid mixture, which was evaporated to dryness as before. The treatment with the acid mixture and evaporation were repeated for the third time when the residue obtained was perfectly white. All traces of perchloric acid were then removed by heating and the residue was moistened with a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The excess of the latter was completely removed by heating the beaker on the water-bath. The dry mass was then treated with a drop of glacial acetic acid and dissolved in 1 or 2 c.c. of water by warming. The solution was filtered into a weighed micro-beaker and the filter paper washed with a small quantity of hot water. The volume of filtrate in the beaker was reduced by evaporation by placing the beaker in its holder on the water-bath. Zinc was then precipitated by sodium quinaldinate. The precipitate was filtered through an Emich's filter-stick, dried in Beneditti-Pichler's drying apparatus and then weighed on a micro-balance. (Rây and Bose, *loc. cit.*). Results of analysis are tabulated below.

TABLE II.

Venoms.	Wt. of venom.	ZnO ₂ .	Zn.	Analysed by	Toxicity value.
I. <i>Naja naja</i>	0.1414 g.	5.2466 mg.	0.5685%	T. C. Sarkar	} 0.035 mg.
"	0.1086	4.0280	0.5670	P. Rây	
II. "	0.1050	3.7580	0.5471	T. C. Sarkar	
"	0.0797	2.7580	0.5290	"	
"	0.1596	5.8170	0.5572	"	
<i>Naja bungarus</i>	0.0512	0.1350	0.0403	S. Ghosh	0.0033
"	0.0536	0.1430	0.4070	"	"
<i>Naja tripudians</i>	0.0553	1.6510	0.4564	H. Bhattacharya	0.03
"	0.0713	2.1390	0.4585	"	"
<i>Bungarus fasciatus</i> (i)	0.1472	0.2770	0.0288	T. C. Sarkar	} 0.37
" (ii)	0.1057	0.1640	0.0237	"	
"	0.1528	0.2380	0.0238	P. Rây	
"	0.1664	0.2690	0.0247	"	

TABLE II (contd.).

Venoms.	Wt. of venom.	ZnO ₂ .	Zn.	Analysed by.	Toxicity value.
<i>Bungarus ceruleus</i>	0.0579 g.	Trace	< 0.02%	S. Ghosh	0.0009 mg.
<i>Vipera russelli</i> (i)	0.1028	0.2450 mg.	0.0380	S. Ghosh	} 0.01
"	0.0860	0.2270	0.0408	"	
" (ii)	0.0752	0.2030	0.0410	"	
<i>Echis carinata</i>	0.0892	1.083	0.1856	S. Ghosh	0.0093
Haemolysin (<i>Naja naja</i>) mixed with mineral salts, NaCl etc.	1.0 50% pure haemolysin fraction	Trace	...	S. Ghosh	9 times more active than crude venom for same N- content.
Neurotoxin (i) (<i>Naja naja</i>) mixed with mineral salts	0.0515 82% neurotoxin fraction	0.4070	0.11≡ 0.15 in neurotoxin	H. Bhattacharya	15 times more active than crude venom for same N- content.
" (ii)	0.0606 82% neurotoxin	0.1680	0.041≡ 0.052 in neurotoxin	"	17 times more active than crude venom for same N- content.

* ZnO₂ = Zinc quinaldinate.

Toxicity values represent the minimum lethal dose for a pigeon 300 g. by weight by intravenous injection.

The results giving values down to 0.025%, demonstrate the sensitivity and the reliability of the method.

My best thanks are due to Dr. B. N. Ghosh of the Department of Applied Chemistry for the supply of neurotoxin and haemolysin fractions of *Naja naja* cobra venom and for determining the toxicity values of the venoms. I express here my thanks also to Mr. A. C. Ray, M.Sc. in the Department of Pharmacology, School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta, for his kindly supplying me a sample of *Echis carinata* venom. All other venoms were purchased from Drug House Ltd., Calcutta.